

Research Article

Quality of life 5 years after cardiac surgery: Preoperative and Postoperative status

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Abstract

A prospective cohort research in Maharashtra state, India, assessed changes in quality of life (QoL) following cardiovascular surgery at two major hospitals. Participated in a study about five years earlier, Data were collected from Jan-2018 to Feb-2023. All willing participants aged 45 to 75 years old with a CAD diagnosis, who could speak and read local/English and were scheduled to have CABG surgery, were invited to participate in a patient-reported health-related quality of life (HRQoL) assessment. Among 175 patients enrolled total participants were 150, aged 45 to 75 undergoing scheduled cardiac surgery during the study period. The characteristics of the study population are shown in Table 1. The patient flow through the study is outlined in Figure 1. All responders are male patients, The mean age when responding was 61.2. Health-related characteristics of the participants (N = 150) five years after coronary artery bypass graft surgery stated in table3.

Health-related characteristics of the participants (N = 150) five years after coronary artery bypass graft surgery, the stress, exercise and perceived health status was improved, the reduced counts of patients numbers shown in case of habits i.e. Smoking and Drinking, than the preoperative health status. Our findings indicate that the physical and mental component of QoL improves considerably up to 5 years following surgery. A questionnaire-based study will not identify all concerns experienced by the patients. Therefore, more information might be obtained by further studies using other designs such as qualitative interview techniques.

Keywords: Quality of life, cardiac surgery, physical and mental component, coronary artery bypass CABG, post-CAB.

Introduction

Coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG), a primary treatment for patients with coronary artery disease (CAD), such as angina pectoris and myocardial infarction, improves cardiac perfusion by bypassing blocked arteries and creating new blood flow pathways using autologous blood vessels. Despite significant drawbacks, including as the requirement for intraoperative median sternotomy and cardiopulmonary bypass, CABG is the most effective treatment for decreasing the recurrence of heart disease as well as mortality.[1] Health-related quality of life (HRQOL) is an individual's subjective perception of physical and mental health [2].The patient-reported HRQOL is a key indicator of the clinical outcome of treatments, including CABG in patients with CAD [3]. Outcome after CABG has traditionally been evaluated using morbidity and mortality rates[4-8]. These are important, objectively measurable adverse outcomes; however, such measurements alone can no longer be regarded as complete. Health-related quality of life (QoL) is a multidimensional construct representing most, if not all, aspects of a person's life[8-18]. Investigation of QoL can provide a more complete understanding of the impact of cardiac surgery on subsequent health status[8-18]. Patients often have post-CABG symptoms such as pain at the incision sites in the chest and leg, respiratory distress, loss of appetite, fatigue, weakness, sleep disturbances, depression, and anxiety [19-23], although it also encompasses the metric of "days alive and out of hospital." [24] Clinical and technical advancements have decreased mortality related to cardiac surgery.[25] Thus QoL has become an outcome of interest because many patients value QoL over quantity of life.[26] QoL represents aspects of one's well-being (eg, physical, psychological, social) that are influenced by one's attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions[27-29]. With improved long-term survival, extended focus on functional status

and HRQOL beyond the first few years after surgery is important. Most studies conclude that HRQOL improves after cardiac surgery procedures, also among elderly patients [30-32]. The aim of this study was therefore to investigate the HRQoL at diagnosis and after the 5 years of surgery, to assess the impact of treatment on HRQoL. Current research largely focuses on a single type of cardiac surgery and approaches QoL with a 2-factor model (physical and mental). Almost all QoL data in cardiac surgery come from secondary analyses of randomized controlled trials in which patients are under heavy scrutiny and have more follow-up than is routine. It is unclear if improvements are due to increased followup or to the procedure itself. Therefore we analyzed QoL after cardiac surgery as a primary outcome in a nonemergent, all-comers population. Indeed, complications such as worsening of psychosocial function may be expected, because patients have to face the challenges of a new life phase that can be accompanied by physical and mental deterioration [33]. It is therefore important for cardiac surgeons to dispose of information about the impact of cardiac surgery on QoL, in order to be able to inform patients appropriately about the pro and cons of the intervention.

Questionnaires

Patient-reported HRQoL was assessed using the Short Form 12 (SF-12). The SF-12 is a generic HRQoL questionnaire of twelve questions taken from the Short Form 36 questionnaire. Understanding how heart surgery affects patients' long-term quality of life can lead to increased patient participation, fully informed consent, and better healthcare outcomes. Current study focuses on a single kind of cardiac surgery and approaches QoL using a two-factor model (physical and mental). As a result, we examined QoL following heart surgery as a main outcome in study.

Methods

A prospective cohort research in Maharashtra state, India, assessed changes in quality of life (QoL) following cardiovascular surgery at two major hospitals. Participated in a study about five years earlier, Data were collected from Jan-2018 to Feb-2023. All willing participants aged 45 to 75 years old with a CAD diagnosis, who could speak and read local/English and were scheduled to have CABG surgery, were invited to participate in a patient-reported health-related quality of life (HRQoL) assessment. The exclusion criteria were: reoperation due to post-CABG complications; patients who were unable to complete the study tools (e.g., hearing impairment) and the patients not able to speak local/English language. In the final analysis, 150 respondents were included after excluding twenty-five with incomplete responses. Only completed SF-12 questionnaires were calculated and included in the analysis. The 12-item Short Form Survey (SF-12) is a general health questionnaire that was first published in 1995 as part of the Medical Outcomes Study (MOS). The SF-12 was constructed using questions drawn from each of the 8 dimensions of the MOS 36 item Short Form Survey (SF-36). It is designed to have similar performance to the SF-36, while taking less time to complete. Two summary scores are reported from the SF-12 – a mental component score (MCS-12) and a physical component score (PCS-12). The scores may be reported as Z-scores (difference compared to the population average, measured in standard deviations). The United States population average PCS-12 and MCS-12 are both 50 points. The United States population standard deviation is 10 points. So each 10 increment of 10 points above or below 50, corresponds to one standard deviation away from the average [34].

Ethical considerations: This study meets the ethical standards outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki, and the institutional review board of Dr. N. Y. Tasgaonkar Institute of Medical Science, Maharashtra, India, obtained ethics

approval. The questionnaire survey was conducted after the researcher explained the purpose of the study to individual potential participants and obtained written informed consent from them.

Figure 1. Consolidated Standards of Reporting Trials (CONSORT) diagram of study participant enrollment. Follow-up data for 150 participants were available.

Data analysis. Data were available on all patients; hence, no patients were excluded before 5 years. The data collected were analyzed using the SPSS WIN 20.0 version. The participants' sociodemographic and disease-related characteristics were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, mean values. Results for continuous variables are expressed as median (range) unless otherwise stated, while scores for questionnaires are expressed as mean (standard deviation, SD). We have used the SF-12 –OrthoTool Kit for summary scores. Only completed SF-12 questionnaires were calculated and included in the analysis. The SF-12 is a generic HRQoL questionnaire of twelve

questions taken from the Short Form 36 questionnaire,²¹ which are grouped into a physical and a mental component summary score (PCS and MCS) and eight multi-item scales: Physical functioning (PF), Role limitation due to physical health (RP), bodily pain (BP), general health (GH), vitality (VT), social functioning (SF), role limitations due to emotional problems (RE), and mental health (MH). The SF-12 scores were transformed to achieve a mean score of 50 and a standard deviation of 10 in the 1998 general U.S. population,^[35] which has been shown to have a good equivalence with country-specific scores in ten Western European countries^[36,37].

Results:

Among 175 patients enrolled total participants were 150, aged 45 to 75 undergoing scheduled cardiac surgery during the study period. The characteristics of the study population are

shown in Table 1. The patient flow through the study is outlined in Figure 1. All responders are male patients, The mean age when responding was 61.2. Health-related characteristics of the participants (N = 150) five years after coronary artery bypass graft surgery stated in table3.

QoL scores

Quality of Life Scores of preoperative and 5 years of follow-up of 150 patient's PCS and MCS scores are given in Table 2. Overall, both component summary scores increased for the first 5 years after surgery, Mean PCS was significantly higher at 5 years than prior to surgery (i.e. 48.56522 to 52.84028) also the MCS was significantly higher at 5 years than prior to surgery (i.e. 52.46772 to 57.83636). Quality of Life Scores preoperative and at 5 years in 150 patients coronary artery bypass graft surgery (PCS and MCS)

Table 1. Sociodemographic and disease-related characteristics of the participants (N = 150) undergoing coronary artery bypass graft surgery (Preoperative Stage)

Variable	Categories	Mean ± SD or n (%)
Male		150 (100)
Age	45-55	50 (33.33)
	55-65	70 (46.66)
	65+	30 (20)
Education	Degree	30 (20)
	Higher Education	50 (33.33)
	Matriculation	52 (34.66)
	Uneducated	18 (12)
Living	Urban	45 (30)
	Rural	105 (70)
Work	Farming	65 (43.68)
	Labour	32 (21.33)
	No work	53 (35.33)
Socio-economic class	Upper middle class	12 (8)
	Middle class	69 (46)
	Skilled working class	35 (23.33)
	Others	34 (22.66)
Stress	Yes	110 (73.33)
	No	40 (26.66)

Diabetes Mellitus	Yes	40 (26.66)
	No	110 (73.33)
Percent of blockage	80-90	48 (32)
	90+	102 (68)
Prior attack	Yes	92 (61.33)
	No	58 (38.66)
Perceived health status	Good	30 (20)
	Average	10 (6.66)
	poor	110 (73.33)
Smoking	Current smoker	30 (20)
	Non-smoker	60 (40)
	Former smoker	60 (40)
Drinking	Current drinker	29 (19.33)
	Non-drinker	35 (23.33)
	Former drinker	86 (57.33)
Exercise	No	70 (46.66)
	Irregular	63 (42)
	Regular	17 (11.33)
Number of diseased vessels	1	17 (11.33)
	2	71 (47.33)
	3	62 (41.33)

The values of PCS and MCS scores before surgery and at 5 years of follow-up are given in Table 2

Time	PCS-12 (Physical Score)	MCS-12 (Mental Score)
Preoperative observation	48.56522	52.46772
5 year after surgery	52.84028	57.83636

PCS, physical component summary score; MCS, mental component summary score of the SF-12

Table 2: Quality of Life Scores preoperative and at 5 years in 150 patients coronary artery bypass graft surgery

In our cohort, both physical and mental components were shown to improve up to 5 years following surgery, showing that the patients appear to have benefited significantly from the surgery, as felt and reported by QoL scores.

Preoperative observation of PCS and MCS

Pertinent Positives:: In general, health is very good; Limited a little in moderate activities; Felt calm and peaceful most of the time; Had a lot of energy a good bit of the time; Felt downhearted and blue a good bit of the time; Physical or emotional health interferes with social activities some of the time;

Pertinent Negatives: Accomplished as much work as would like (unaffected by emotional problems); Works as carefully as usual (unaffected by emotional problems); No interference of pain with normal work.

Table 3. Health-related characteristics of the participants (N = 150) five years after coronary artery bypass graft surgery.

Variable	Categories	Mean \pm SD or n (%)
Stress	Yes	36 (0)
	No	114 (76)
Perceived health status	Good	110 (73.33)
	Average	30 (20)
	poor	10 (6.66)
Smoking	Current smoker	00 (0)
	Non-smoker	60 (40)
	Former smoker	90 (60)
Drinking	Current drinker	00(0)
	Non-drinker	35 (23.33)
	Former drinker	115 (76.66)
Exercise	No	5 (3.33)
	Irregular	13 (8.66)
	Regular	132 (88)

The table 3 shows that the Health-related characteristics of the participants (N = 150) five years after coronary artery bypass graft surgery, the stress, exercise and perceived health status was improved, the reduced counts of patients numbers shown in case of habits i.e. Smoking and Drinking, than the preoperative health status shown in Table1.

Postoperative observation of PCS and MCS (5years)

Pertinent Positives: A little bit of interference of pain with normal work; Had a lot of energy some of the time; Felt downhearted and blue a good bit of the time; Physical or emotional health interferes with social activities a little of the time.

Pertinent Negatives: In general, health is excellent; Accomplished as much work as would like (unaffected by physical health); Not limited in kind of work or other activities in last week (unaffected by physical health); Accomplished as much work as would like (unaffected by emotional problems); No interference of pain with normal work; Felt calm and peaceful all of the time; Had a lot of energy all of the time; Felt downhearted and blue none of the time; Physical or emotional health interferes with social activities none of

the time. Our results shows the similarity of PCS increased positively from 48.56 to 52.84 with J. Burisch, stated the only those in Western Europe experienced a significantly more positive perception of HRQoL, rising from 49.9 to 54.9 [39]. Scores below 50 indicate worsening symptoms, above 50 reflect symptom improvement, and 50 signifies no change [38]. In our study, MCS showed a significant improvement over baseline up to 5 years after surgery. This is consistent with a Polish study of health-related QoL in 140 patients undergoing CABG surgery, who were found to have higher MCS at 5 years than PCS. The authors concluded that physical limitations persist after CABG that affect physical functioning but do not affect emotional or mental functioning as much. [40]. Some limitations must be considered when evaluating the findings of our research. The study was done at a single institution, which may restrict generalizability and introduce institutional bias in patient selection and postoperative treatment. In addition, because this was not a randomized controlled study, some confounding could still exist. Patient selection criteria and the spectrum of preoperative morbid diseases usually differ among research, making valid comparisons challenging. [41].

Discussion

Our data suggest that coronary artery bypass graft surgery can have a considerable and long-term favourable effect on QoL as measured by the SF12. Precise information on the impact of heart surgery on QoL is critical for both patients and surgeons as they balance both the benefits and risks of the procedure. Several things contribute to improved performance. Patients are likely to report considerable symptom reduction post-operatively, which has a direct influence on their overall sense of wellbeing. Functional restrictions may improve, enabling patients to reengage in activities they previously loved. Following surgery, patients may become more motivated to maintain good lifestyle habits. These behavioral modifications may be encouraged by invested relatives and/or friends, hence boosting the patient's perceived social support. From a psychological perspective, awareness of increased heart function could reduce health-related anxiety. Our findings indicate that the physical and mental component of QoL improves considerably up to 5 years following surgery. A questionnaire-based study will not identify all concerns experienced by the patients. Therefore, more information might be obtained by further studies using other designs such as qualitative interview techniques.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CABG = Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting
 QoL = Quality of Life
 HRQoL= Health-Related Quality Of Life
 SF = Social Functioning
 SF-12 = Short-Form Health Survey
 MCS = Mental Component Score
 PCS = Physical Component Score

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Competing interests

No author has any competing interests to declare.

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